

THE HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE OF LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL DEPARTMENTS OF REGIONAL INTERNAL AFFAIRS DEPARTMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the emergence of organizational departments of territorial internal affairs bodies, the legal basis of their activities, its history.

KEY WORDS

Regional internal affairs departments, legal basis, analysis, criminogenic situation, organizational Department, work with appeals.

In our country, comprehensive work has been carried out aimed at improving the system of internal affairs bodies, strengthening their lower branches closer to the population, clearly defining the tasks and functions of structures of all levels, rational distribution of forces and means taking into account modern risks, and so far such work has been carried out. In particular, many measures are being developed to improve the efficiency of the activities of each structure, to strengthen its position in maintaining public order. Over the past years on this path, we have witnessed the formation of many new structures, the improvement of the activities of existing ones, the adoption of regulatory legal acts defining their tasks and powers.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev in his work "Strategy of new Uzbekistan" said that "To communicate directly with the people, we have established a completely new system for the positive solution of people's concerns, problems - Nation receptions and virtual receptions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the activities of state organizations we established "work in the section of neighborhoods", "access to the people", "listen to his pain", "deal with anxiety and solve problems on the place"¹, - he had set urgent tasks for everyone. He had indicated and made a task to all branches of management should work directly with them.

Since the internal affairs bodies are a branch of the public administration system, they have been promoting the reform of the public administration system. On the basis of the changes taking place in the socio-political life of our country, the internal affairs bodies are also revising their tasks, structure, goals.

¹Sh.M.Mirziyoyev "Strategy of new Uzbekistan" Tashkent 2021 y 46-page

The measures implemented made it possible to increase the role of internal affairs bodies, to transform them into a socially oriented professional structure, which is unconditionally fulfilled by each employee his duty of service — “to serve the benefits of the people”. Among the population, the sense of trust and respect is growing from year to year for the activities of the internal affairs bodies of citizens, its employees who fulfill their duty in various field services. At the same time, there are a number of systemic drawbacks in the organization of the daily activities of the internal affairs bodies, which are manifested in insufficient coordination of the management of forces and means, educational work with personal composition and their professional skills, prevention of violations and ensuring targeted control-analysis of the fight against crime at a lower level. In order to overcome these shortcomings and problems, a program of various measures was developed. For example, the strategy of Action for 2017-2021, approved in 5 priority areas of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, also sets out several priorities that should be implemented in order to introduce effective management, control and work with personal composition into the activities of the internal affairs bodies. They include:

first of all, taking place an effective mechanism for the distribution and management of the internal affairs bodies in a coordinated way by taking into account the real rapid and criminal situation;

secondly, identifying a systematic analysis of the practical problems in the field of public order preservation, prevention of offenses and combating crime, and aimed at forecasting the criminogenic situation;

thirdly, establishing a qualitatively new, simplified procedure for admission to the Ministry of internal affairs bodies, providing for the concentration of positions with candidates of high spiritual and moral, working and professional qualities;

fourth, to implement of an effective system for conducting educational work with personal content, including the study of their service and family-household problems through the targeted application of scientific and psychological methods;

fifth, to organize an influential departmental control over the performance of tasks aimed at unconditionally ensuring legality, strict adherence to service discipline and timely detection of violations committed by employees;

sixth, improving the mechanism of proceedings and the procedure for the circulation of documents, ensuring the timely, uniform and complete

implementation of regulatory legal acts in all branches of the system of internal affairs bodies.²

In order to improve the activities of existing organizational departments in the system of internal affairs bodies, to increase regulatory and Legal Regulation, in accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 23, 2018 “on measures to introduce an effective system of management, control and work with personal composition of internal affairs bodies” PQ-3919, the Organizational Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs was established on the basis of the Department of work and proceedings with appeals of individuals and legal entities.

The department has the right to independently study the effectiveness of the implementation of the established tasks, evaluate the management staff and make proposals for improving the operational and service activities of the internal affairs bodies.³

In accordance with the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Internal affairs bodies” and the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-3919 of August 23, 2018, the Minister of Internal Affairs “To organize of activities of the organizational Department of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated September 7, 2018 in order to further improve the system of management, control, analysis, legal.

According to this order, 6 applications have been approved. They are as follows:

Regulation of the organizational Department of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to appendix 1;

Model regulations of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the main Department of internal affairs of the city of Tashkent and the organizational departments of the internal affairs departments of the regions according to appendix 2;

Model regulation on the organizational department (divisions) of the internal affairs bodies of the district (city, network) according to appendix 3 ;

Regulation of the application acceptance group (Call center) according to annex 4;

List of analytical units of the Ministry of internal affairs field services according to appendix 5;

² The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-3919 of August 23, 2018, paragraph 2

³ The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-3919 of August 23, 2018, paragraph 6

The model regulation of the organizational departments of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of internal affairs of city of Tashkent and the internal affairs departments of regions (territorial internal affairs bodies) defines their status, main tasks and functions, rights and responsibilities.

The department is considered a structural unit of territorial internal affairs bodies and is directly subordinate to the heads of territorial internal affairs bodies.

In its activities, the department is responsible for the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the House of Commons, decisions and decrees of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, law about “Internal affairs bodies”, normative acts of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, territorial internal affairs bodies- it follows the legal acts of the Ministry of internal affairs and other laws and regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on June 4, 2017, Order No. 136 “on approval of exemplary regulations on territorial divisions of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan”.

The structure of the administration consists of:

Organizational and control unit (territorial control and Inspectorate unit, departmental control unit);

Department of Organization of Duty Services (methodological support group; part of duty);

Department of information and analysis (division (group) of integrated analysis and forecasting of the operational situation; group of analysis and assessment of the activities of the industry services);

Department of legal provision (legal expertise Group; Legal Analysis Group; contractual-legal group);

Secretariat (proceedings Group; enforcement group);

Referral processing unit (group);

International cooperation and foreign Experience Study Group;

Reference group;

Cadre group;

Chancellery;

System 102.

The department is headed by a chief who is appointed and relieved of his post by the Minister of Internal Affairs on the basis of a submission entered by

the head of the territorial internal affairs body in coordination with the head of the organizational Department.

The head of the department will have 3 deputies appointed in the order established by the heads of territorial internal affairs bodies.

The department is directly subordinate to the heads of the territorial internal affairs bodies, is their working body and, according to their assignments, develops and adopts management decisions aimed at improving the operational-service activities of the internal affairs bodies.

The heads of the Departments of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of internal affairs of the city of Tashkent and the internal affairs departments of the regions have the right to provide independent information directly to the heads of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of internal affairs of the regions.

Employees of the department carry out their activities on the basis of functional obligations approved in the prescribed manner.

The current work plans of the department are approved by the head of the territorial internal affairs bodies.

Control over the activities of the department is carried out by the head of the territorial internal affairs body.

Proceedings and privacy procedures are carried out independently by the administration in the manner established by law.

In conclusion, it should be said that, based on the above information, we got an idea of the organizational Department, the stages of organizing the activities of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of internal affairs of the city of Tashkent and the organizational departments of internal affairs of the regions.

List of literature used:

1. Constitution Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan. 2023 y
2. Law about "Internal affairs bodies"
3. Sh.Mirziyoyev "New Uzbekistan strategy" Tashkent. 2021 y
4. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan of August 23, 2018 about "Measures to introduce an effective system of management, control and work with personal composition of internal affairs bodies" PQ-3919
5. Order of the minister of internal affairs of September 7, 2018 about "The organization of activities of the organizational Department of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan"

